
Series: PHYSICS

Khmelnik S.I.<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1493-6630>

Particle – spherical standing wave

Annotation

It is shown that one of the solutions to Maxwell's equations in spherical coordinates is a spherical wave, which can be identified with a particle that is both a particle and a wave. This creates a mathematical description of the particle-AND-wave, as opposed to the particle-OR-wave described by modern quantum physics, which cannot be both at the same time. This particle rotates, this phenomenon is observed (most likely) in experiments and is described as spin - a certain quality of elementary particles that has no analogue in the macrocosm. The existence of a rotating particle-I-wave destroys the boundary between the microworld and the macroworld: both worlds can be described by a single classical electrodynamics.

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1. Introduction

In [1, Chapter 4] the mathematical model of the so-called wave-AND-particle (WIP), which constantly and simultaneously exhibits both wave and particle properties. HIV is a standing wave that exists in a confined space of vacuum. It does not have its own speed and can, like a particle, move at an arbitrarily low speed; it has energy, an internal flow of

energy and mass. In [1] it is shown that such a wave can exist in the volume of a cube. Below we prove that such a wave can exist in the volume of a sphere.

2. Maxwell's equations in spherical coordinates

In [2, 3], a solution to Maxwell's equations in spherical coordinates was found. The known solution for a spherical electromagnetic wave does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy (it is conserved only on average), the electric and magnetic intensities of the same name (in coordinates) are in phase, only one of Maxwell's system of equations is satisfied, the solution is not a wave one, there is no energy flow with a real value. The proposed solution is free from these shortcomings. Maxwell's system of equations, being a system of partial differential equations, has many solutions. The applicability of a solution to physics is determined by a single criterion: it must satisfy the law of conservation of energy (LEC). The existing solution does NOT satisfy this law.

So, let's consider the system of Maxwell's equations for vacuum, which has the form

$$\text{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \tag{A}$$

$$\text{rot}(H) - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = 0, \tag{B}$$

$$\text{div}(E) = 0, \tag{C}$$

$$\text{div}(H) = 0, \tag{D}$$

where

E - electric field strength,

H - magnetic field strength,

μ - absolute magnetic permeability,

ε - absolute dielectric constant.

Next, spherical coordinates are considered - see Fig. 1. Maxwell's equations in spherical coordinates in the absence of charges and currents have the form given in table. 1.

Figure 1.

Table 1.

1	3
1	$\frac{E_\varphi}{\rho \operatorname{tg}(\theta)} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\rho \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial t} = 0$
2	$\frac{\partial E_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} - \frac{E_\varphi}{\rho} - \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial \rho} + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial t} = 0$
3	$\frac{E_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\rho \partial \varphi} + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial t} = 0$
4	$\frac{E_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial \rho} + \frac{E_\theta}{\rho \operatorname{tg}(\theta)} + \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\rho \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} = 0$
5	$\frac{H_\varphi}{\rho \operatorname{tg}(\theta)} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\rho \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial t} = 0$
6	$\frac{\partial H_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} - \frac{H_\varphi}{\rho} - \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial t} = 0$
7	$\frac{H_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\rho \partial \varphi} - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial t} = 0$
8	$\frac{H_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial \rho} + \frac{H_\theta}{\rho \operatorname{tg}(\theta)} + \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\rho \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} = 0$

In the solutions found, the strengths are determined by formulas of the following form:

$$E_{\varphi} = \frac{e_{\varphi}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (1)$$

$$E_{\theta} = \frac{e_{\theta}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (2)$$

$$E_{\rho} = \frac{e_{\rho}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (3)$$

$$H_{\varphi} = \frac{h_{\varphi}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (4)$$

$$H_{\theta} = \frac{h_{\theta}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (5)$$

$$H_{\rho} = \frac{h_{\rho}}{\rho} \text{Khm}(\theta, \alpha) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (6)$$

where Khm is some function, $\alpha, \chi, \omega, e_{\varphi}, h_{\varphi}$ are constants. We will consider a special case when

$$\alpha = 20. \quad (7)$$

In this case

$$\text{Khm}(\theta, 20) = \sin(\theta) \quad (8)$$

and the system of equations (1-6) is simplified:

$$E_{\varphi} = \frac{e_{\varphi}}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (9)$$

$$E_{\theta} = \frac{e_{\theta}}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (10)$$

$$H_{\varphi} = \frac{h_{\varphi}}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \cos(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (11)$$

$$H_{\theta} = \frac{h_{\theta}}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \sin(\alpha \varphi + \chi\rho + \omega t), \quad (12)$$

In [3] it is shown that

$$e_{\varphi} = e_{\theta}, \quad (13)$$

$$h_{\varphi} = -h_{\theta}. \quad (14)$$

$$h_{\varphi} = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_{\theta}, \quad (15)$$

$$h_{\theta} = -\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_{\varphi}, \quad (16)$$

3. Energy of the sphere

Energy Density

$$W = \frac{1}{8\pi} (\varepsilon H^2 + \mu E^2) \quad (1)$$

From the previous formulas it follows that

$$W = \frac{\varepsilon e_{\varphi}^2}{4\pi\rho^2} \sin^2(\theta). \quad (2)$$

All the energy of an electromagnetic wave in a sphere of radius R :

$$W = \frac{\pi \varepsilon e_{\varphi}^2}{2R}. \quad (3)$$

4. Energy flows in the sphere

In [3] it is shown that in a sphere there are only energy flows passing along a radius inclined at an angle. The density of this energy θ .

$$S_{\rho} = \frac{c}{4\pi\rho^2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} (\sin(\theta) \cdot e_{\varphi})^2. \quad (1)$$

This means that the energy flow passing along the radius remains constant over time, which corresponds to the law of conservation of energy. This also means that on each circle defined by the values θ and ρ (see green circle in Fig. 1), there is a standing electromagnetic wave.

Let us find the ratio of energy flux density (1) to energy density (3.2):

$$S_{\rho}/W = \frac{c}{4\pi\rho^2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} (\sin(\theta)e_{\varphi})^2 / \sin^2(\theta) \frac{\varepsilon e_{\varphi}^2}{4\pi\rho^2} = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} / \frac{c}{\varepsilon} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}} \quad (2)$$

Because then $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu}}$,

$$S_{\rho}/W = c^2. \quad (3)$$

5. Rotation of a standing wave

Let's look at the green circle again in Fig. 1, on which there is a standing electromagnetic wave. In this wave, magnetic and electrical intensities fluctuate (in time) - see (2.9-2.12).

Let's find the speed of rotation of this circle when changing. Obviously, this speed is equal to the derivative of the function given implicitly in the form of these equations. Consider, for example, function (2.11). We have: H_{φ}

$$\frac{d(H_{\varphi})}{d\varphi} = h_{\varphi} \frac{d}{d\varphi} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\alpha h_{\varphi} \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t),$$

$$\frac{d(H_{\varphi})}{dt} = h_{\varphi} \frac{d}{dt} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\omega h_{\varphi} \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t).$$

Then the angular velocity of rotation of the spherical electromagnetic wave

$$\omega_{\varphi} = \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{d(H_{\varphi})}{dt} / \frac{d(H_{\varphi})}{d\varphi} = \frac{\omega}{\alpha}. \quad (3)$$

Thus, there is a rotation speed of the electromagnetic wave pulsating on the green circle. This speed does NOT depend on the radius of the circle. This means that the entire circle in which the green circle is located rotates, and therefore the entire spherical electromagnetic wave rotates with angular velocity. around the z axis. ω_{φ}

6. Mass of a spherical wave

We will use the well-known Umov formula, which connects the energy density and energy flow with the speed of energy movement:

$$v = \frac{S}{W}. \quad (1)$$

It is also known that the pulse density

$$p = \frac{W}{v}, \quad (2)$$

and the mass

$$m = \frac{p}{v} = \frac{W}{v^2}. \quad (3)$$

Hence,

$$m = \frac{w^3}{s^2}. \quad (4)$$

In (4.3) it was shown that

$$\frac{S}{W} = c^2. \quad (5)$$

From (4, 5) we find;

$$m = \frac{w}{c^2}. \quad (6)$$

We have obtained a known ratio.

7. Rotation energy

Section 5 shows that a spherical electromagnetic wave rotates at a catch speed

$$\omega_\varphi = \frac{\omega}{\alpha}. \quad (1)$$

Density of the moment of inertia of the wave relative to the central axis

$$j = mr^2, \quad (2)$$

where the radius of rotation of the mass is determined by a formula of the form

$$r = \rho \sin(\theta) \quad (3)$$

- see fig. 1. Therefore,

$$j = m\rho^2 \sin^2(\theta). \quad (4)$$

Energy density of the rotational motion of the wave

$$Q(r) = mr^2 \omega_\varphi^2 = m\rho^2 \sin^2(\theta) \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 \quad (5)$$

or, taking into account (6.6),

$$Q(r) = \frac{W}{c^2} \rho^2 \sin^2(\theta) \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2. \quad (6)$$

or, taking into account (3.2),

$$Q(r) = \frac{\varepsilon e_\varphi^2}{4\pi c^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 \sin^4(\theta). \quad (7)$$

Thus, similar to mass m and energy W , in a spherical wave there is a moment of inertia j and energy Q of rotational motion. Let us find the energy of the rotational motion of the wave in a sphere of radius R :

$$W_o = \frac{\varepsilon e_\varphi^2}{4\pi c^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 \int_0^R \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \left(\int_0^{2\pi} (\sin^4(\theta) d\theta) \right) d\varphi \right) d\rho =$$

$$= \frac{\varepsilon e_\varphi^2}{4\pi c^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 R \int_0^{2\pi} \left(\int_0^{2\pi} (\sin^4(\theta) d\theta) \right) d\varphi = \frac{\varepsilon e_\varphi^2}{4\pi c^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 R \left(2\pi \frac{3}{4}\pi\right)$$

or

$$W_o = \frac{3\pi\varepsilon}{8} \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha c}\right)^2 e_\varphi^2 R. \quad (8)$$

8. Spherical wave - particle

So, we have obtained a mathematical description of a spherical wave in which

- There are no radial strengths,
- There are radial energy flows,
- Strengths form standing electromagnetic waves,
- The wave energy has a constant value,
- Energy flows have a constant value,
- There is an electromagnetic mass created by an oscillating flow of electromagnetic energy,
- An electromagnetic wave rotates around a certain axis,
- There is wave rotational energy created by the rotation of electromagnetic mass.

All these characteristics of the wave allow us to identify it with a particle, which is simultaneously both particle and wave. We received a mathematical description particles-AND-waves, unlike particles-OR-waves, which modern quantum physics describes and which cannot be both at the same time.

This the particle rotates. This phenomenon is observed (most likely) in experiments and is described as spin - a certain quality of elementary particles that has no analogue in the macrocosm. The existence of a rotating particle-AND-wave destroys the boundary between the microworld and the macroworld: both worlds can be described by a single classical electrodynamics.

9. Ball lightning

There is no apparent limitation on the size of a spherical rotating particle-I-wave. Such a formation appears to be some types of ball lightning. In [4] we read:

A large number of testimonies, described in detail in the literature [5, 6, 7], make it possible to identify a number of properties of BL that are repeatedly repeated in various documents and therefore have a high degree of reliability:

1. *high energy density - thousands of joules per cubic centimeter.*
2. *abnormally high specific energy density [5],*
3. *no does not interact with powerful air flow,*
4. *are attracted to pipes, ... holes, cracks,*
5. *break plastic objects into small pieces,*
6. *at a distance of several meters they are capable of melting part of the glass in the closed aluminum frame of the camera's sighting hole, they heat the rings put on the finger,*
7. *pass freely through glass and wire insulation without damaging them, sometimes evaporating or melting small holes,*
8. *usually do not have thermal radiation,*
9. *are observed as luminous plasma or corona discharge-emitting balls, sometimes having a gray or black color; transparent BLs have been described [7],*
10. *often there is strictly parallel movement along walls, ground, metal surfaces,*
11. *when the BL is destroyed, an explosion is heard, an electric shock, or a powerful discharge into the ground may occur; the appearance of a luminous crown,*
12. *the lifetime of a BL can be tens of seconds; black BLs exist for several days [7].*
13. *can occur instantly inside enclosed spaces at considerable distances from surrounding objects.*

You may notice that many of the items on this list can be explained by the fact that BL is a spherical wave.

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